

21st Century School Heads Instructional Leadership and Management Skills: A Basis For A Proposed Intervention Plan

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Abstract

This descriptive-comparative study assessed the instructional leadership and management skills of school heads from Gattaran East, West, and Central Districts in Cagayan, Philippines, during the 2024-2025 school year, using data from school heads through total enumeration and teachers through simple random sampling with Slovin's formula. A survey questionnaire based on DepEd Memorandum No. 024 s 2020 - Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads was utilized to assess the instructional leadership and management skills of school heads. Findings revealed school heads were mostly middle-aged, female, doctorate holders, Principal II positions, with moderate years of service and extensive trainings. Both groups rated instructional leadership as Outstanding in assessment of learning, program implementation, and supervision, but Very Satisfactory in program development and adaptation. Management skills were Outstanding across operations, fiscal management, and technology use. Significant differences emerged in the assessment of learning, with teachers noting greater resource-related challenges such as facilities and supervision. Schools were mostly small, at basic SBM levels, and Outstanding in OPCR ratings. Conclusions highlight gaps between groups, signaling needs for enhanced SBM practices despite high performance. A proposed intervention plan recommends targeted DepEd training, capacity-building, dissemination of findings, and implementation of collaborative, technology-enabled strategies to bridge gaps and advance instructional excellence.

Keywords: *Gattaran District, instructional leadership, intervention plan, management skills, perception gaps, 21st century school heads, Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads, School-Based Management SBM*

Introduction

A 21st-century school head is not merely an administrator but a visionary instructional leader and effective manager who aligns resources, systems, and personnel to improve teaching and learning and promote student success. As education aims to equip individuals with the skills and confidence needed for meaningful societal participation, the Philippine basic education system has undergone significant transformations, including changes in instructional modalities, the implementation of the K–12 curriculum, and the challenges brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic. These developments have intensified the demand for adaptive, innovative, and transformative school leadership committed to inclusive and high-quality education.

The roles and responsibilities of school heads in the Philippines are legally anchored in Republic Act No. 9155, or the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, which institutionalized school-based management and redefined school heads as both instructional leaders and administrative managers. RA 9155 grants school heads authority and accountability to set the school vision and mission, improve teaching and learning processes, manage human and material resources, and promote shared leadership to ensure quality education.

School administrators play a vital role in achieving learning outcomes by overseeing school operations and strengthening instructional leadership through teacher collaboration and professional development, consistent with RA 9155's framework of decentralized and participatory governance. In the districts of Gattaran West, Gattaran Central, and Gattaran East in Gattaran,

Cagayan, school heads demonstrate these competencies by articulating a clear learning vision aligned with national and global trends and by using data to inform resource allocation, teacher development, and school improvement planning. However, influencing classroom instruction remains a critical challenge, particularly within the principal-agent relationship between school leaders and teachers.

Instructional supervision, as defined by the Department of Education (DepEd), is a continuous and collaborative process aimed at improving instruction through guidance, support, and monitoring. This practice is anchored in key DepEd policies, including the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) (DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017), the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH) (DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2020), and the Philippine Professional

Standards for Supervisors (PPSS) (DepEd Order No. 25, s. 2020), which operationalize the leadership and management expectations set forth in RA 9155.

As cited by Basilio et al. (2021) identified a number of barriers to effective and efficient secondary education monitoring in the twenty-first century within the framework of the Nigerian educational system. These include a lack of funding, unstable political conditions, a lack of qualified and experienced workers, poor scheduling, and subpar facilities. Accordingly, the managerial skills construct is a crucial aspect to consider, which is why this study was conducted.

This study aligns closely with Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4) of the United Nations' 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, which seeks to "ensure inclusive and

equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all." By assessing and strengthening school heads' instructional leadership and management skills, the research directly supports SDG 4 targets such as building safe and effective learning environments (4.a) and enhancing teacher training (4.c), addressing barriers like resource gaps and supervision challenges to foster effective leadership that drives student achievement and educational equity in the Philippine context.

A 21st-century school leader inspires a learning culture, builds strong teams, and steers the school through both challenges and innovation with clarity and compassion. As a 21st-century school head, studying instructional leadership and management skills is essential to meet the evolving demands of modern education. Rapid changes in technology, curriculum, and learner diversity require school heads to move beyond traditional administrative roles and lead teaching and learning effectively. This study identified strengths and gaps in key leadership competencies, providing a basis for an intervention plan that supports continuous professional growth. The findings may inform capacity-building initiatives and leadership development programs, ultimately enhancing school effectiveness, teacher performance, and student achievement.

Thus, this study aimed to assess the instructional leadership and management skills of the 21st century School Heads of Gattaran West District, Gattaran Central District and Gattaran East District, Gattaran Cagayan for the School Year 2024-2025.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to assess the instructional leadership and management skills of the 21st century School Heads of Gattaran East, West, and Central Schools, Gattaran Cagayan for the School Year 2024-2025.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the school head-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Highest Educational Attainment
 - 1.4 Plantilla Position
 - 1.5 Length of Service as School Head
 - 1.6 Trainings Attended
2. What is the assessment of the two groups of respondents in the instructional leadership and management skills of the school in terms of:
 - 2.1 Instructional Leadership
 - 2.1.1 Assessment of Learning
 - 2.1.2 Developing Programs and/or Adapting Existing Programs
 - 2.1.3 Implementing Programs for Instructional Improvement
 - 2.1.4 Instructional Supervision
 - 2.2 Management Skills
 - 2.2.2 Managing School Operations
 - 2.2.3 Fiscal Management

- 2.2.4 Use of Technology in the Management of Operations
3. Is there a significant difference on the assessment of the two groups of respondents in the instructional leadership and management skills?
 4. What is the profile of the school-respondents in terms of:
 - 4.2 SBM Level of Practices
 - 4.3 School Size
 - 4.4 Performance Indicators
 - 4.5 Office Performance Commitment and Review Form
 5. What are the issues and concerns encountered by the respondents in the instructional leadership and management of the school?
 6. What intervention plan can be proposed to address the issues and concern encountered by the respondents in the instructional leadership and management of the school?

METHODS AND PROCEDURES

Research Design

The study employed descriptive-comparative research design to describe the profile and the school head and school respondents and their instructional leadership and management skills, and to test the difference on the assessment of the two groups of respondents in the instructional leadership and management skills. This design was appropriate because it effectively combines descriptive elements with comparative analysis to examine variations between groups.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were the eight (8) School Heads of Gattaran West, eight (8) School Heads of Central, and five (5) School Heads of East Districts in Gattaran consisting a total of twenty-one (21) school head-participants using total enumeration and one hundred seventy-four (174) teachers-respondents from the three (3) districts using simple random sampling. Slovin's formula was used in selecting the teacher-respondents of the study. The table below shows a clear picture of the distribution of the respondents.

Table 1

Distribution of Respondents of the Study

Name of School	Number of Respondents		Total
	School Head	Teachers	
Gattaran West Central School	1	11	12
Guising Elementary School	1	7	8
Basao Elementary School	1	8	9
Ganzano Elementary School	1	7	8
Nassiping Elementary School	1	8	9
Fe Roullette Danao	1	8	9
Aguguican Elementary School	1	8	9
L Adviento Elementary School	1	6	7

Nabaccayan Central Elementary School	1	10	11
Batug- Palagao Elementary School	1	9	10
Baraoidan Elementary School	1	7	8
TASICA Elementary School	1	8	9
Newagac Elementary School	1	10	11
Naddungan Elementary School	1	10	11
Barbarit Elementary School	1	7	8
Batug Sur Elementary School	1	7	8
Gattaran East Central School	1	12	13
Pina Este Elementary School	1	8	9
Mabuno Integrated School	1	9	10
Cumao Elementary School	1	8	8
Capissayan Norte Elementary School	1	7	8
Total	21	174	195

Data Gathering Tool

The researcher utilized a survey questionnaire to gather the data needed in the study. The main instrument used in the study was based on the DepEd Memorandum Number 024, s,2020 titled, “National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads”. The survey questionnaire has four parts.

Part I is on the profile of the school head-respondents as to age, sex, highest educational attainment, plantilla position, length of service as school head, and trainings attended;

Part II is on the assessment on the instructional leadership as to assessment of learning, developing programs and/or adopting existing programs, implementing programs for instructional improvement, and instructional supervision, and on management skills in terms of managing school operations, fiscal management, and use of technology in the management of operations;

Part III is on the profile of school-respondents as to SBM level of practices, school size, performance indicators, and office performance commitment and review form; and

Part IV is on the issues and concerns encountered by the respondents in the instructional leadership and management of the school.

Data Gathering Procedure

The research followed a systematic process in gathering the data need for the study.

First, prior to data collection, the researcher sought institutional approval by submitting a formal letter to the University President through the Institutional Review Board (IRB) Chair. The letter was noted by the research adviser and conformed by the Dean of the Graduate School. An Ethics Clearance was then secured from the IRB office, verifying the study's adherence to ethical standards such as informed consent.

Second, to access the target population, the researcher sent a formal request letter to the Schools Division Superintendent of the Department of Education (DepEd) in Cagayan Province. Upon approval, purposefully selected respondents were provided with the survey questionnaire, along with a cover letter explaining the study's purpose, to elicit their assessments.

Lastly, the researcher personally administered the survey questionnaire to the respondents during scheduled sessions at their respective schools. The respondents were assured of anonymity, data confidentiality, and that their responses would be used solely for research analysis. The collected information and data were then analyzed statistically.

Statistical Tools

The data gathered were tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted using the following tools:

Frequency count and percentage distribution were used to analyze the profile variables of the respondents.

Weighted mean was used to analyze the assessment of the two groups of respondents in the instructional leadership and management skills of the school, as well as the issues and concerns they encountered in the instructional leadership and management of the school. These were further interpreted using the 5-point Likert scale below:

Numerical scale	Numerical Range	Descriptive Interpretation
5	4.50 - 5.00	Outstanding/ Very Great Extent
4	3.50 – 4.49	Very Satisfactory/Great Extent
3	2.50 – 3.49	Satisfactory/Moderate Extent
2	1.50 – 2.49	Unsatisfactory/Little Extent
1	1.00 – 1.49	Poor/Very Little Extent

Moreover, ANOVA was used to test the difference on the assessment of the two groups of respondents in the instructional leadership and management skills of the school.

Summary of Findings

The following are the key findings of the study:

1. Profile of the School Head-Respondents
 - Majority of school head-respondents are aged between 42 to 46 years old, female, married, doctorate graduates, holds Principal II plantilla position, with 6 to 10 years of length of service, and attended school-based to international trainings and seminars.
2. Assessment of the two groups of respondents in the instructional leadership and management skills of the school
 - 2.1 Instructional Leadership

Teacher-Respondents

- Teachers assessed the instructional leadership of the school, as outstanding among assessment of learning, implementing programs for instructional improvement, and

instructional supervision dimensions, while developing program and/or adapting existing program was assessed as very satisfactory

School Head-Respondents

- School Heads assessed the instructional leadership of the school, as outstanding among assessment of learning, implementing programs for instructional improvement, and instructional supervision dimensions, while developing program and/or adapting existing program was assessed as very satisfactory

2.2 Management Skills

Teacher-Respondents

- Teachers assessed the management skill of the school as outstanding across all dimensions

School Head-Respondents

- School Heads assessed the management skill of the school as outstanding across all dimensions

3. Comparison the assessment of the two groups of respondents on the instructional leadership and management skills

Instructional Leadership

- There is significant difference on the assessment of the two groups of respondents in the instructional leadership in terms of Assessment of learning.

Management Skills

- There is no significant difference on the assessment of the two groups of respondents in the management skills of the School across dimensions.
4. The profile of the school-respondents
 - In the SBM Level of Practices, 11 or 52.38 percent in terms of school size, 19 or 90.48 percent. Regarding the OPCR (Office Performance Commitment and Review) Rating, all schools received an "Outstanding" rating (100%),
 5. The issues and concerns encountered by the respondents in the instructional leadership and management of the school.
 - In the resource-related issues, teachers again rated challenges more highly, with mean scores between 3.94 and 4.33, indicating that they experience significant concerns regarding school resources, including safe facilities, student supervision, and the deployment of resources.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, the researcher concluded that instructional leadership and school management skills in the participating schools were generally rated as Outstanding by both teachers and school heads, particularly in managing school operations, fiscal management, and the use of technology. However, significant discrepancies emerged between the two groups in

their perceptions of leadership and management issues. Teachers reported greater challenges in areas related to leadership, resources, stakeholder engagement, and fiscal management, while school heads perceived these issues to a much lesser extent. Additionally, most schools were small and not yet accredited under the School-Based Management (SBM) framework, indicating substantial room for growth in institutional capacity, shared governance, and inclusive leadership practices despite their high-performance ratings.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following are here by recommended:

1. DepEd Regional and Division Offices may design, fund, and implement targeted training and mentoring programs aligned with the school-Based Management (SBM) framework to monitor progress and provide technical assistance to ensure effective implementation at the school level.
2. School heads may participate in capacity-building efforts and cascade leanings to their teaching staff. Continuous professional development programs should focus on instructional leadership, financial management, and use of technology in school operations
3. The results and findings of this study may be disseminated during DepEd's regional in-service training (INSET), division learning action cell (LAC) sessions, or School-Based Management (SBM) assessment forums to raise awareness of perception gaps in instructional leadership and management.
4. School heads may implement the proposed plan to strengthen and sustain instructional leadership and management competencies through targeted, research-informed, collaborative, and technology-enabled interventions that support instructional excellence, effective management, and School-Based Management (SBM) advancement.
5. Future research may explore the underlying factors contributing to the perception gap between teachers and school heads regarding instructional leadership and management challenges. A qualitative or mixed-methods approach—such as interviews, focus group discussions, or case studies—could provide deeper insights into the contextual, cultural, or organizational dynamics influencing these differing views.

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